

ESSENCE OF DEVELOPING LEARNERS' COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE

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ANNOTATION

Skill is a way of doing an action. In linguodidactic testing, the object of control is communicative skills, which might be understood as the ability of a person to carry out a speech action to solve certain communicative tasks derived from acquired skills and knowledge. The skill is formed through exercises and creates the ability to perform actions.

Key words: *skill, competence, communicative skill and competence, external and internal components.*

Introduction

Having studied the different interpretation of the concept of "Skill", it may be decided to use the following definition of this concept: "Skill is the mastery of the methods (techniques, actions) of applying acquired knowledge in practice". Various communicative aspects were already considered at the beginning of the development of methodological ideas by O. A. Alexandrova, M. V. Grigoryeva, and M. E. Dashkin. They believed that one of the most important goals of education should be precisely the preparation of students for practical activities. [1]

Methodology

Communicative skills are understood as the ability to correctly, intelligibly, adequately and competently convey one's thought, to perceive information from

communication participants in interpersonal communication. According to G. M. Andreyeva, communicative skills are a complex of conscious communicative actions, which are based on a sufficiently high theoretical and practical readiness of the person, contributing to the creative use of knowledge to reflect and transform reality. [2]

Data collection and analysis

A. V. Mudrik defines the concept of communicative skills as skills associated with the correct alignment of their behavior i.e. it is necessary to understand human psychology: to be able to choose the right intonation and gestures correctly, to be able to understand other people, to try to predict the reaction of the interlocutor, to imagine oneself in his/her place, to be able to correctly choose the most correct way to address different interlocutors. [3]

The primary sources of communicative skills from rhetorical positions are rhetorical skills, namely:

1. The ability to invent and find material;
2. The ability to arrange material in the correct (logical) sequence;
3. The ability to consistently express thoughts;
4. The ability to memorize pre-prepared speech;
5. The ability to deliver a prepared speech using sound means of emotional-

semantic expressiveness [4]

Result and Discussion

According to A. V. Mudrik, the components of communicative skills include: objective perception of people (understanding of their character and mood); orientation of partners; the ability to correctly understand the communicational situation (to understand the rules, to establish new contacts); to cooperate in various types of activities (plan and set goals) and to analyze what has been achieved. [3] N. I. Zhinkin believed that there was a need to pay attention to what pupils say and how they respond to the actions and actions of other people. It is necessary to identify their thoughts and feelings that accompany the schoolchildren's acts of their communication with other people, their difficulties that they encounter when coming into contact with others. He defined the external and internal components of communication. External components

include verbal (speech utterances) and non-verbal forms of behavior (tone of voice, pace of speech, facial expressions and gestures). [5]

The developing of communicative skills remains an urgent problem since the level of formation of communicative skills affects not only the effectiveness of children's education, but also the process of their socialization and personality development in general. Skills are formed in the course of activity, and communicative skills are formed and improved in the direct process of communication. Formation is the process of shaping something[6]; in a broad sense, formation is understood as any process in which stability is given to something, completeness, a certain type or something which is created, organized, composed or combined.

Conclusion

In education system, insufficient attention is paid to the work on the formation of communicative skill; therefore, there is no basis for the further development of these skills among middle-level pupils. Most often, in the work on the development of speech, the age characteristics of the pupil are not fully taken into account. Pupils think specifically and are not always able to establish an internal relationship between the word and the image.

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